

D4.2 Engagement & Community Report - b

Revision: v.1.0

Work package	WP4	Task	Task 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4
Submission date	26/06/2025	Due date	30/06/2025
Deliverable lead	OpenNebula Systems	Version	1.0
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Abstract	This document provides detailed information about the community structure implemented by the Project and the definition and execution of the engagement actions involving the European research and industry ecosystem, as well as other relevant initiatives and user communities across different sectors. It is an ongoing deliverable with an initial version in		

	M6, the current version in M18, and a final version to be published in M30.
Keywords	Community, engagement, ecosystem, research, industry, forum, strategic alignment.

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
V0.1	15/04/2025	Agreed version of TOC, ready to start editing	Chiara Zincone (OpenNebula Systems)
V0.2	15/05/2025	Included content Sections 2, 3, 4, 5	Chiara Zincone (OpenNebula Systems), Amrita Prasad (Martel Innovate), Enrique Areizaga Sanchez (Tecnalia), Danijel Pavlica (F6S), Tajana Medakovic Dautovic (F6S)
V0.3	23/06/2025	Updated sections 2, 3, 4, 5 following reviewers' feedback	Chiara Zincone (OpenNebula Systems), Amrita Prasad (Martel Innovate), Enrique Areizaga Sanchez (Tecnalia), Alberto P. Marti (OpenNebula Systems)
V0.4	25/06/2025	Updated formatting with coordinator's feedback	Chiara Zincone (OpenNebula Systems)

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Project co-funded by the European Commission in the Horizon Europe Programme		
Nature of the deliverable:	R	
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	X

SEN	<i>Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement</i>	
Classified R-UE/ EU-R	<i>EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444</i>	
Classified C-UE/ EU-C	<i>EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444</i>	
Classified S-UE/ EU-S	<i>EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444</i>	

Executive summary

Deliverable D4.2 "Engagement & Community Report" provides detailed information about the updated community structure implemented by the Project and the definition and execution of the engagement actions involving the European research and industry ecosystem, as well as other relevant initiatives and user communities across different sectors, up until the end of M18 (June 2025).

During the reporting period, the Project has launched a series of impactful actions focused on stakeholders' engagement and community building, building upon the activities carried out up until M6.

This document outlines how the project has established a robust structure of thematic and geographic Working Groups (WGs), successfully creating a platform for collaboration between EU industry leaders, researchers, and strategic international partners—particularly in Japan and South Korea. These WGs not only serve as forums for discussion and alignment but also play a pivotal role in shaping the Research & Innovation Roadmap that underpins the project's strategic vision.

The report highlights NexusForum.EU's close cooperation with major European initiatives like the IPCEI-CIS and the European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud, ensuring strategic alignment with EU priorities on digital sovereignty and open source. The project's engagement with a diverse ecosystem—including SMEs, cooperatives, policymakers, and academic institutions—has surfaced critical needs such as a clear definition of "European Open Source" and the mapping of sovereign technology layers.

Additionally, the project has positioned itself as a key actor in promoting convergence among European initiatives, offering an inclusive space for policy influence, cross-border collaboration, and coordinated action on pressing digital challenges. The stakeholder consultations, webinars, and outreach activities are not only shaping EU R&I priorities but are also fostering new partnerships and thought leadership on cloud-edge-IoT and AI ecosystems in Europe and beyond.

This is the M18 version of an ongoing deliverable with an initial version in M6 (June 2024) and subsequent, updated versions to be delivered in M30 (June 2026).

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CRA	Cyber Resilience Act
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
DCA	Data Governance Act
HE	Horizon Europe
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
IDSA	International Data Spaces
IoT	Internet of Things
IPCEI	Important Project of Common European Interest
IPCEI-CIS	IPCEI Next Generation Cloud Infrastructure and Services
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
R&I	Research and Innovation
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
TF	Task Force

1 Introduction

Deliverable D4.2 provides detailed information about the community structure implemented by the Project and the definition and execution of the engagement actions involving the European research and industry ecosystem, as well as other relevant initiatives and user communities across different sectors. It is the updated version of D4.1 (June 2024). It will be updated again by M30 (June 2026).

This document follows the structure of the corresponding tasks in the Project's WP4 "Stakeholders' engagement and community building". It is composed on an Introduction (Chapter 1) and five main chapters:

- Chapter 2, describing the community building and cross-cooperation structure set up by the Project up until M18.
- Chapter 3, describing how the Project is engaging with the European research and innovation ecosystem, and its priorities after M18.
- Chapter 4, describing how the Project is engaging with the European market and industry stakeholders, and its priorities after M18.
- Chapter 5, describing how the Project is working towards a strategic alignment with other relevant initiatives.
- Chapter 6, which provides the conclusions and identifies the main next steps.

The document ends with three additional sections:

- Appendix A, with two examples of the public interviews that the Project has continued to carry out during its execution with EU industry leaders and technology experts.
- Appendix B, with a summary of the feedback received by the Consortium as part of the session led by the Project at the Smart Connectivity and Computing Workshop in Tokyo, Japan (March 2025).
- Appendix C, with a table detailing why each Co-Leader was chosen for each Working Group, in a biographical form.

2 Community building and cross-cooperation structure

The community building and cross-cooperation structure is the foundation upon which we have been building a solid and long-lasting community for NexusForum.EU. This structure guides the collaboration with (and among) the EU research and industry ecosystems, integrating relevant strategic initiatives in the development of the European Cognitive Computing Continuum, and actively engaging user communities across various sectors and domains. A key mechanism for achieving this objective is the Consortium's unique ability to align and actively involve EU companies directly participating in the IPCEI-CIS and the *European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud*, as well as those organisations involved in relevant Horizon Europe consortia.

A key component of the project is the establishment of multiple Working Groups, that are both aligned with the main topics of the Research & Innovation Roadmap produced by NexusForum.EU and with similar topics covered by the IPCEI-CIS and the *European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud*. These WGs create a unique context for transversal collaboration and engagement between EU industry experts and researchers, focusing on specific topics. Each Working Group is co-led by a top researcher from one of the research partners in the NexusForum.EU consortium (or, sometimes, and external expert) plus one representative from a participating EU private company. The Co-Leaders of all WGs form the Research & Innovation Roadmap Advisory Board of the Project. This body plays a key role in producing the consolidated Roadmaps by channelling and evaluating the feedback obtained from the EU industry and research community, and from non-EU entities and experts.

Structure of the Working Groups

The NexusForum.EU Working Groups can be classified into two categories.

- **Thematic working groups**, based on the main sections of the Research & Innovation Roadmap and aligned with the strategic vision of the IPCEI-CIS and the *European Alliance for Industrial Data Edge and Cloud*, hold as main objective to collect contributions and feedback from relevant EU industry experts and researchers.
- **Geographical working groups** aim at fostering links between the EU cloud-edge-IoT ecosystem and the industry and research ecosystems of other strategic non-EU countries. It is indeed through these working groups that international cooperation with Japan and South Korea is envisioned.

The NexusForum.EU Working Groups are structured in a way that ensures an alignment of the Research & Innovation Roadmap's thematic sections with both the IPCEI-CIS and the *European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud*. Four NexusForum.EU Working Groups follow the topics of the IPCEI-CIS Workstreams, whereas the other four are aligned with the original Task Forces from the Cloud-Edge WG at the *European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud* (see Table 1 below).

NexusForum.EU Working Group	Co-Leader stakeholder affiliation	Initiative alignment and role
Telco Cloud-Edge	Telefónica	<i>Coordinator IPCEI-CIS Workstream 1</i>
AI for Cloud-Edge	OpenNebula Systems	<i>Coordinator IPCEI-CIS Workstream 2</i>
Cloud-Edge for AI	E-Group	<i>Coordinator IPCEI-CIS Workstream 3</i>
Cloud-Edge Use Cases	Engineering	<i>Coordinator IPCEI-CIS Workstream 4</i>
Cybersecurity	Arthur's Legal, Strategies & Systems	<i>Member of Cloud-Edge WG, European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud</i>
Sustainability	T-Systems	<i>Member of Cloud-Edge WG, European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud</i>
Interoperability	IONOS	<i>Member of Cloud-Edge WG, European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud</i>
Sovereignty & OpenSource	OpenNebula Systems	<i>Co-leader of the Open Source TF at Cloud-Edge WG, European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud</i>

Table 1: How the Working Groups align with the IPCEI-CIS Workstreams and the Cloud-Edge WG of the European Alliance of Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud

To ensure effective coordination and collaboration, Working Groups as well as a **Community Forum** open to all participants, are hosted on Whaller¹ (see the Project’s Deliverable D5.1 for further details), a secure collaborative and social platform developed and maintained in France. Working Groups host discussions and community-building actions per topic, involving relevant EU industry experts and researchers. Each Working Group has an industry Co-Leader and a research Co-Leader, who coordinate the activities carried out by their respective WGs, with the help of selected Consortium members.

Fig. 1: NexusForum.EU collaborative platform provided by Whaller.

¹ <https://my.whaller.com/org/portal/21622>

As shown in Figure 1, so far, the eight thematic Working Groups are active, as well as one of the geographic working groups: the EU-Japan Cooperation one. The EU-South Korea Working Group is yet to be launched at the time of writing, as the industry Co-Leader is to be appointed.

2.1.1 The Research & Innovation Roadmap Advisory Board

At the time of writing, the Research & Innovation Roadmap Advisory Board entails the nine active Working Groups and the NexusForum.EU Consortium. As mentioned in the previous sections, each Working Group is co-led by an industry and research stakeholder, ensuring smooth collaboration across the duration of the CSA, and contributing towards supporting the European Commission (EC) and the European cloud-edge-IoT ecosystem in a holistic way.

This Advisory Board (Figure 2) acts as a strategic cooperation and alignment body between the NexusForum.EU Project, the IPCEI-CIS, and the *European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud*, as well as integrating points of view coming from Japan and soon, from South Korea, with the aim of fostering international cooperation. It is through the guidance of this Advisory Board that the Working Groups perform research, analyse, and work (internally and together) towards the definition and continuous improvement of the Research & Innovation Roadmaps that the project will produce during its execution. Anyone can apply to be part of one or more Working Groups via a dedicated online form² however, for those Working Groups that align with the IPCEI-CIS and with the European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud, only members whose represented stakeholder is headquartered in the European Union are accepted. However, for the two geographical Working Groups that foster international cooperation with Japan and with South Korea, an exception is made.

Research Co-Leaders have been identified from within the RTOs participating in the NexusForum.EU consortium (i.e. RISE, Tecalia and Meiji University), whereas other private companies have agreed to contribute to the project with an industry Co-Leader to act as their counterpart in each of the Working Groups. To this day, the Research & Innovation Roadmap Advisory Board is structured as pictured in the visual below. Furthermore, the eight Working Groups that are co-led by an industrial partner headquartered in the European Union, are aligned with the IPCEI-CIS and with the Cloud-Edge WG of the *European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud*.

² <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/NexusForum.EUEUWorkingGroups>

Figure 2: The Research & Innovation Roadmap Advisory Board

Lastly, the Co-Leaders of the Working Groups have been informed about their duties via two Kick-Off Sessions, during which they were instructed on what the Project is about, its aims and objectives, and how the Working Groups are expected to function (see Figure 3 for reference). These sessions were also recorded and made available through the Community Forum. The Co-Leaders are expected to hold regular meetings, during which they engage with the members of their Working Group on the given topic, and discuss any new developments and any priorities to be included as part of the feedback to the Research & Innovation Roadmap.

Figure 3: One of the two NexusForum.EU Kick-Off Sessions for WG Co-Leaders

2.1.2 NexusForum.EU Community Engagement Strategy

To foster stakeholder participation and support the long-term sustainability of the European Computing Continuum, NexusForum.EU has implemented a structured community engagement strategy. This strategy facilitates active and meaningful interaction among stakeholders across research, industry, policy, and civil society, ensuring that insights and perspectives inform the project's roadmap and related activities.

- The main objective is to build a cross-sectoral and multidisciplinary community of stakeholders who actively engage through the NexusForum.EU Community Forum contribute to Working Groups, and participate in webinars, open and public consultations, and roadmap validation processes. The following instruments have been deployed to support onboarding, retention, and activation of the community:
 - **Call-to-Action (CTA) at Events:** Each activity that is open to the public (e.g. webinars, workshops, the annual Summit) includes a clear and recurring call-to-action encouraging participants to join the Working Groups.
 - **Welcome Email:** Upon registering for a NexusForum.EU event or expressing interest in a WG, stakeholders receive a welcome message with direct links to the Community Forum and Working Groups, along with a short overview of engagement opportunities.
 - **Onboarding Document:** A concise, visual briefing note (1-page PDF/slide) titled *“How to Engage with NexusForum.EU”* to facilitate first-time stakeholder orientation. It highlights the benefits of participation in the Working Groups and outlines key entry points, and consultation mechanisms.
 - **Social media Cards and Digital Assets:** A series of branded visuals are used to promote WG activities, highlight speaker insights, showcase polls and consultations, and share event invitations. These assets are disseminated via project newsletters and social media, and partner channels.
 - **Monthly Community Digest:** A monthly summary email is set to be circulated to registered stakeholders, highlighting WG discussions, open policy consultations, upcoming events, and selected contributions from the Community Forum.

F6S and OpenNebula Systems implement and coordinate this strategy, with support from Martel for dissemination and communication activities. WG Co-Leaders play a key role in driving engagement within their thematic communities, while all partners contribute to

onboarding stakeholders and amplify the reach and impact of the NexusForum.EU Community and more broadly, of the scopes of the project, through their networks.

2.1.3 NexusForum.EU Working Group Webinars

The NexusForum.EU Working Group Webinar Series is a targeted mechanism for visibility, engagement, and policy relevance across the project's WGs. It aligns with the European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud, and IPCEI-CIS, serving as a platform for dialogue, knowledge exchange, and co-creation among stakeholders from research, industry, policy, and civil society.

Each webinar disseminates WG themes and early results while validating outputs through participatory discussion. This ensures WG activities remain aligned with the evolving needs of the CEI ecosystem and the broader EU policy landscape, including public consultations on digital infrastructure and sovereignty.

The series aims to kick off, present, and validate WG contributions; foster expert and community dialogue on emerging tech and regulatory challenges; co-shape strategic direction; integrate feedback into roadmap updates; and align with the European Commission's policy calendar.

Key audiences include NexusForum.EU members, EU project participants, industry (SMEs and large firms), academia, policymakers, and technical communities—with special focus on engaging European Alliance and IPCEI-CIS partners for coherence across initiatives.

Expected outcomes include increased WG visibility, stronger stakeholder engagement, and input for the final roadmap and WP3 policy recommendations. Webinars will also support sustainability planning, EU policy dialogue, and cooperation with Japan and South Korea.

Running from June to November 2025, the 30-minute sessions are interactive roundtables or fireside chats led by WG Co-Leaders from research and industry. Emphasizing openness and accessibility, the webinars foster conversation on WG themes and challenges rather than formal presentations.

2.2 Engagement with the broader EU ecosystem

In the current cloud and edge jurisdictional and geopolitical context, NexusForum.EU acts as an engagement tool, which benefits its joining members in many ways. Indeed, the tensions on the Eastern border of the EU, the rise of cybercrime, and the ever-growing digital market share held by non-EU hyperscalers have highlighted the crucial role of sovereignty for an interoperable and secure cloud, edge and data infrastructure. The Data Act, the Digital Markets Act and the AI Act are, among others, legal instruments enacted by the European Union in a joint, supranational, effort to leverage market dynamics and sustain competition, as well as supporting innovation in the cloud edge data domain.

It is in this context that the NexusForum.EU Project acts as a collaborative umbrella, under which stakeholders can openly exchange best practices, broaden their networks in the cloud edge data field and influence the European ecosystem. Members of the Working Groups have access to a unique network of experts and to a newsfeed tool to receive the latest news on cloud and edge computing in Europe, as well as with the latest developments on relevant EU regulation, relevant to the project. An example of dissemination within the Community is shown in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: News dissemination on the Community Forum about a recent Consultation on the Cloud and Apply Development Act

The NexusForum.EU’s ties with the IPCEI-CIS also allow stakeholders to meet the industry leaders behind the multibillion project and to have preferential access to the NexusForum.EU Summits, as well as other events which would have a limited quota of participants. The project also held a Smart Computing and Connectivity Workshop in Tokyo³, Japan, which convened experts from the industry, research institutions and policy makers to engage in impactful discussions on the latest developments in the field of the Computing Continuum, as well as serving as an in-person tool to recruit new members for the EU-Japan Cooperation Working Group. The Research & Innovation Roadmap has been made available for feedback and contributions on Whaller before its second, updated version, is published and before the global cloud-edge-IoT ecosystem is consulted on its contents. The Co-Leaders of the Working Groups are partly responsible for channelling such feedback to the Roadmap.

³ [EU-Japan Digital Week 2025 - INPACE Hub](#)

Figure 5: The NexusForum.EU Wiki page.

Lastly, the European research ecosystem will be invited to join an online, high-level catalogue of cutting-edge research, in line with the topics of the Research & Innovation Roadmap. This wiki (see Figure 5) is meant to, at Community level, showcase the research work done in the areas of the Computing Continuum, and to, at stakeholder level, guarantee a level of visibility in those areas.

2.3 Channelling contributions to the Research & Innovation Roadmap

The Research & Innovation Roadmap Advisory Board collects feedback from the whole NexusForum.EU Community (see Figure 6). Co-Leaders have editorial rights.

Fig. 6: How the NexusForum.EU Working Groups and contribute to the Research & Innovation Roadmap

The NexusForum.EU Summits in Brussels, and other relevant events such as the Smart Computing and Connectivity Workshop in Tokyo, were also leveraged in order to invite private companies, academics, users, and policymakers, to explore new joint exploitation actions between EU research and industry actors, and to collect valuable feedback from the EU and non-EU cloud-edge-IoT ecosystem.

An example of such consultation is the feedback session organised at the most recent event held in Tokyo, to gather feedback about the Roadmap, priorities for future Horizon Europe programmes extending to Japan, and recruit members for the Japan Working Group. The details of this feedback session, which will be considered for the enhancement of the next version of the roadmap, can be found in Annex B.

3 Engagement of European research and innovation ecosystem

NexusForum.EU has contributed towards the support and consolidation of the EUCloudEdgeloT initiative across all its activities. The Consortium has collaborated with the sister projects OpenContinuum and Unlcok-CEI - which in the meantime have concluded their activities - as well as the ongoing project of CEI-Sphere, to manage, support and foster the European research and innovation ecosystems.

3.1 Engagement with the RIA and IA ecosystem through the EUCloudEdgeloT initiative

NexusForum.EU co-leads the EuCloudEdgeloT (EUCEI) Task Force 6 (on communication) together with Unlock-CEI (until December 2024) and CEI-Sphere from January 2025. Task Force 6 is the only active task force of the EUCEI initiative, which comprises all the projects under the EUCEI community. Currently these are the 6 MetaOS projects, 5 swarm computing projects, 9 cognitive cloud projects, 7 cognitive computing continuum projects, 4 Open Source projects, and 7 other research and innovation projects from the related clusters like Data that have joined the EUCEI community for the purpose of support towards communication, dissemination and collaborations. The 2 newly funded pilots Innovation actions namely O-CEI and Cop-Pilot have also joined Task Force 6.

NexusForum.EU runs a monthly task force call with the community where the most recent news and updates are shared. This is also the platform where we discuss and brainstorm on upcoming events, webinars/workshops, collaborations for white papers, book chapters, contributions towards surveys etc.

In the NexusForum.EU Summit, the project also had sessions where experts and representatives of the projects have been invited to contribute to panels and discussions and/or showcase their project's outputs and key exploitable results.

In the NexusForum2024 Summit, we organised a "RIAs Presentation and Pitch Session". The overall objective of this session was to:

- Highlight the challenges that the RIAs have seen in their field of research.
- Highlight the project's main innovations, and the use cases where the project's platform is being validated.
- How is that project helping "your cluster specific topic eg. Swarm computing, metaOS, Cognitive Computing continuum etc" of research and innovation progress Europe's vision towards digital sovereignty.

In this session, 10 RIAs of the EuCEI community participated: AC3, aerOS, CoGNETs, EMPYREAN, FluidOS, MYRTUS, OASEES, SovereignEdge.COGNIT, TaRDIS and Vitamin-V.

They showcased advances in federated orchestration, AI trust layers, decentralized data processing, and domain-specific architectures across agriculture, mobility, and industry. This session was widely praised by participants and some noted a need for deeper exploration of deployment results in future editions.

The RIAs of the EuCEI community were also given an opportunity to host a booth. The booths were presented in the main catering area of the event to maximise visibility and networking opportunities

3.2 Engagement with other relevant EU-funded initiatives

NexusForum.EU also engages with several European funded (partially or fully) initiatives, such as the Big Data Value Association, Data Spaces Support Center, IDSA, Gaia-X, HiPEAC, the European Cloud Alliance, FIWARE. The project has invited experts from these organisations to its events or organised sessions to gain valuable inputs regarding their take on the European cloud-edge-IoT strategy and its future. Examples of this are the NexusForum Summits (more detailed information on the NexusForum2024 Summit is reported in D5.3 Communication and Dissemination Plan and Report), the Project's organised session at European Big Data Value Forum 2024, where the panel discussion was focused on Consolidating research and policy along the cognitive computing continuum the Smart Connectivity and Computing Workshop in Tokyo on 31st of March 2025 (collaboration with INPACE), participation at the Gaia-X MarketX event on 13-14 May in Valencia where we took the opportunity to engage the participants in a survey for the SWOT analysis for the development of the EU digital policy recommendations. For further information, the engagement with INPACE is detailed in the Project's deliverables D3.2 and D5.2.

Their inputs and feedback will also be considered on NexusForum.EU's Research & Innovation Roadmap document.

4 European market and industry engagement

4.1 Engagement with the IPCEI-CIS ecosystem

The IPCEI-CIS, supported by 12 EU Member States, is now investing €1.2 billion in State aid to support research, development and the first industrial deployment of European innovations in cloud and edge technologies, an initiative that is expected to unlock an additional €1.4 billion in private funds.⁴

Figure 7: IPCEI-CIS General Assembly in Gdańsk (Poland), in March 2025⁵

The NexusForum.EU Project has established a special relationship with the IPCEI-CIS, given that OpenNebula Systems chairs its Industry Facilitation Group. This is fostering the coordination of actions and the alignment between both initiatives.

On the 27 & 28 March 2025, the second General Assembly of the IPCEI-CIS took place, this time in Gdańsk, Poland (see Figure 7). During the event, the Facilitation Group announced the definition of the first version of the IPCEI-CIS Reference Architecture. In anticipation to its public release at the end of June 2025[?], the NexusForum.EU has organised on the 19th June 2025[?] a meeting with all the Working Group Co-Leaders of the Project to launch a new initiative for producing a collaborative map of cloud & edge technologies based on the IPCEI-CIS Reference Architecture (see Figure 8). The final objective is to create a dynamic, public map of European technologies targeting its specific functional blocks, while identifying critical applications and gaps in the stack that should be covered in the future through joint research and innovation.

⁴ <http://www.ipcei-cis.eu/>

⁵ [Common European Interest in computing technologies](#)

Figure 8: Functional blocks of the IPCEI-CIS Reference Architecture.

4.2 Engagement with the European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud

Launched in 2021, the Cloud-Edge WG of the *European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud*, through its Cloud-Edge WG, is currently involved in producing several outputs that are highly relevant for NexusForum.EU:

- A Thematic Roadmap for Open Source
- A Thematic Roadmap for Trust Principals

As part of the alignment with the EU Cloud Alliance, NexusForum.EU (through its Advisory Board) is going to lead the production of a common definition of “European Open Source”, a complex concept involving control by European entities and alignment with sovereignty goals. While open source thrives on global collaboration, there is a recognized need to balance this with geopolitical interests by developing a clear criteria, shared by industry and academia, on which open source technologies and governance models qualify as being “under European control”. This is a basic step for the EC to be able to define a comprehensive open source policy supporting competitiveness and digital sovereignty.

Furthermore, the Cloud-Edge Working Group of the Alliance has also produced its Telco Cloud Reference Architecture (see Figure 9).

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REPORT / STUDY | Publication 28 February 2025

European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud releases its Reference architecture for Telco Cloud

Following the publication of the Telco Cloud Thematic Roadmap in July 2024, this new deliverable, called the Telco Cloud Reference Architecture (TCRA) sets a reference for the constitutive elements of Telco Cloud solutions

Telco Cloud refers to a scalable and elastic pool of shareable physical or virtual resources that meet the requirements of network functions and services.

This [Reference Architecture](#) provides technical guidance for operators throughout the telco edge value chain (telco operators, edge operators, cloud providers) on how to design and deploy their services.

Fig. 9: The European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud released already its Reference Architecture for Telco Cloud, under the coordination of OpenNebula Systems, in February 2025 (Source: EC website⁶).

Lastly, the Project's Research and Innovation Roadmap was presented during the 5th General Assembly of the European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud (see Figure 10), where attendees were also invited to join the NexusForum.EU Working Groups.

Figure 10: RISE presenting the NexusForum.EU Research and Innovation Roadmap at the 5th General Assembly of the European Alliance of Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud.

⁶<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/european-alliance-industrial-data-edge-and-cloud-releases-its-reference-architecture-telco-cloud>

4.3 Engagement with the broader EU digital industry

One of the main objectives of the NexusForum.EU Project will be to ensure a permanent and solid engagement with the broader EU digital industry with interests in the research and innovation actions that are taking place around cloud and edge computing, and to encourage their participation in the consultation processes launched by EU institutions but also their active involvement with the CSA through its Working Groups for EU experts and researchers. Until M18 (June 2025), the project has focused its efforts on consolidating the effective engagement with the following EU-based industrial entities:

CECOP

<https://cecop.coop>

CECOP is the European confederation of industrial and service cooperatives. CECOP represents 27 members in 16 European countries. CECOP is the European regional organisation of CICOPA, the world sectoral organisation for industry and services, which is in turn part of the International Cooperative Alliance (ICA).

Efforts to engage with CECOP are based on the understanding that European tech cooperatives have one of the highest potentials in terms of becoming early adopters of the cloud and edge computing technologies developed by some of the key strategic initiatives taking place in the EU, including the IPCEI-CIS. Conversations with Mondragon Corporation, a major player in CECOP and presiding company of the larger CICOPA, are still on-going.

Cloud Infrastructure Services Providers in Europe (CISPE)

<https://cispe.cloud>

CISPE is a non-profit association with a goal of developing greater understanding and promoting the use of cloud infrastructure services in Europe. CISPE has developed the first dedicated cloud infrastructure Code of Conduct for Data Protection under the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) that would probably be the first of its kind. The code aligns with the strict requirements laid out in the GDPR framework to help providers comply and avoid penalties while helping customers and end users to select cloud providers and trust their services.

CISPE is a big advocate at EU level for a cloud first public procurement policy, sustainable energy-efficient policies, security and privacy, an open and competitive IT environment, a balanced policy framework distinguishing when cloud providers have access to their customers' data or not, and a coherent and ambitious global trade agenda for the international deployment and use of cloud infrastructure that promotes European values with key trading partners.

Cloud Data Engine (CDE) unveiled at VivaTech June 2025 the first software suite designed to monitor the compliance of cloud services with Gaia-X trust frameworks—a key milestone for the operationalization of sovereign and interoperable data ecosystems in Europe. This pioneering solution will enable real time, automated verification of Gaia-X labels for cloud services integrated into marketplaces and federated data spaces ensuring that governance rules and transparency requirements are enforced from design to deployment. This software suite will be fully integrated to support full orchestration of the new release of the CISPE

Catalogue starting at the end of June 2025, which already features more than 1,000 located cloud services from CISPE members.

European Cloud Industrial Alliance (EUCLIDIA)

<https://www.euclidia.eu>

EUCLIDIA is an association of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) involved in the cloud computing sector. The mission of EUCLIDIA is to ensure that Europe continues to benefit from the innovation and technological advancements developed within the continent. EUCLIDIA is committed to creating a robust ecosystem and an SME-friendly environment that promotes innovation.

EUCLIDIA's objectives align with the targets of NexusForum.EU, particularly in promoting R&D among European SMEs. NexusForum.EU has engaged with EUCLIDIA to ensure that relevant SMEs were represented in the roadmaps produced by the CSA (e.g. by encouraging EUCLIDIA members to join the project's Working Groups for EU experts and researchers), and to collect timely policy recommendations through the public consultations launched by NexusForum.EU.

European DIGITAL SME Alliance

<https://www.digitalsme.eu>

The European DIGITAL SME Alliance is the largest network of ICT small and medium enterprises in Europe, representing more than 45,000 companies. Efforts to engage with this entity are based on the understanding that European digital SMEs have one of the highest potentials in terms of becoming early adopters of the cloud and edge computing technologies developed by some of the key strategic initiatives taking place in the EU, including the IPCEI-CIS. Conversations with the European DIGITAL SME Alliance are already on-going.

As shown in Figure 11, the NexusForum.EU Project has already started to participate in some of the events organised by the European DIGITAL SME Alliance on digital sovereignty and engaged with the Alliance via LinkedIn, supporting the action with a communication and dissemination post. This webinar was also advertised via the NexusForum.EU Community Forum, and some of the members joined the webinar to enrich the discussion.

Figure 11: Engagement with the European DIGITAL SME Alliance via the NexusForum.EU LinkedIn channel.

4.4 Engagement with relevant non-EU industrial actors

The NexusForum.EU Project will also ensure an active engagement with the broader non-EU digital industry with interests in the research and innovation actions that are taking place in Europe around cloud and edge computing. This engagement will be focused on fostering participation in the consultation processes that the CSA will launch as part of the post-publication collection of feedback on its Research & Innovation Roadmaps. After M6 (June 2024), the project has been focusing its efforts on consolidating the effective engagement with non-EU industrial actors through the following entities and initiatives:

EU-Japan Centre for Industrial Cooperation

<https://www.eu-japan.eu>

Joint venture established in 1987 by the European Commission (DG GROW) and the Japanese Government (METI) for promoting all forms of industrial, trade and investment cooperation between the EU and Japan. Its activities include offering support services for EU entities targeting Japan, designing training schemes & sectoral missions in Japan, promoting R&D and innovation, maintaining the National Contact Point in Japan for Horizon Europe, and conducting policy analysis.

The NexusForum.EU Project leverages the well-established network and resources it offers to identify the Japanese industrial counterparts of those EU tech companies interested in joint R&I activities around cloud and edge computing, so that they both can join the

EU-Japan Working Group. This Centre was present at the NexusForum Summit 2024 with a booth, where it had the opportunity to engage with the multitude of attendees, to hold insightful discussions about the topics of the ecosystem's fields.

EU Business Hub

<https://eubusinesshub.eu>

The EU Business Hub is a project funded by the European Union in support of EU Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) and startups within the green, digital, and healthcare sectors that seek business opportunities and establish partnerships in Japan and the Republic of Korea (RoK). It will organise 10 business missions in Japan and 10 in the Republic of Korea by the end of 2027, each business mission allowing a group of approximately 50 innovative EU companies to benefit from extensive business coaching and B2B matchmaking.

The NexusForum.EU Project is planning to leverage this initiative in order to identify the Japanese / South Korean industrial counterparts of those participating EU tech companies interested in joint R&I activities on cloud and edge computing, so that they both can join the upcoming EU-Japan and EU-South Korea Working Groups that the NexusForum.EU CSA is planning to set up as part of its Community Forum.

Japan Business Council in Europe (JBCE)

<https://www.jbce.org>

Created in 1999, the JBCE is a leading European organisation representing the interests of more than 100 multinational companies of Japanese parentage active in Europe. Its members operate across a wide range of sectors, including information and communication technology, electronics, chemicals, automotive, machinery, wholesale trade, precision instruments, pharmaceutical, steel, textiles and glass products. The JBCE has shown a particular interest in a number of EU files related to digital policy and innovation, including the AI Act, the Data Act, the Cyber Resilience Act, and the development of the European Data Health Space and the European Mobility Data Space.

During the Smart Connectivity and Computing Workshop in Tokyo, the NexusForum.EU project engaged with several Japanese stakeholders operating in the EU. These were stakeholders with a special interest in R&I activities, and the interactive session was an opportunity for them to be aware of cloud and edge computing, and more broadly about the CSA. For example, Fujitsu, a Japanese stakeholder operating in the EU as well, accepted to Co-lead the EU-Japan Working Group, and to be part of the NexusForum.EU Community.

Korea Business Association Europe (KBA Europe)

<https://kba-europe.com>

Launched in 2013, KBA Europe is a business interest group that represents concerns and advocates the interests of Korean companies operating in Europe. We also seek to strengthen the strategic partnership between Korea and the EU to deal with the common challenges both businesses are facing. The JBCE has shown a particular interest in a number of EU files related to digital policy and innovation, including the GDPR, the DMA, the DSA, the Chips Act, and the Data Act.

The main objective for the NexusForum.EU Project after M18 (June 2025) will be to ensure that South Korean tech companies operating in the EU and with a special interest in R&I activities on cloud and edge computing are aware of the CSA, with a special focus on the upcoming EU-South Korea Working Group that is going to be set up as part of its Community Forum.

Korea Industrial Intelligence Association (KOIIA)

Korea Industrial Intelligence Association

Established to promote the advancement of Korea's information industry, the Korea Information Industry Association (KOIIA) serves as a central platform supporting ICT companies in Korea through policy advocacy, research and development support, as well as fostering digital transformation. KOIIA actively engages with stakeholders across the public and private sectors to drive innovation and competitiveness in areas such as AI, big data, cloud computing, and next-generation networks.

As part of the NexusForum.EU Project, KOIIA's role after M18 (June 2025) will focus on ensuring that Korean ICT stakeholders involved in the fields of the Cognitive Computing Continuum are informed about the CSA and are actively engaged in the upcoming EU–South Korea Working Group under the project's Community Forum framework.

5 Strategic alignment with relevant initiatives

5.1 Engagement with relevant associations, foundations, and collective initiatives

5.1.1 The Path to Convergence

The main update compared to the previous document is the identification, by the different associations, of an urgent path towards ‘convergence’.

Starting with the Data Spaces Business Alliance (DSBA) including Gaia-X European Association for Data and Cloud AISBL, the Big Data Value Association (BDVA), FIWARE Foundation, and the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA). Together they represent 1,000+ leading key industry players, associations, research organizations, innovators, and policymakers worldwide. With this cross-industry expertise, resources and know-how, the Alliance drives awareness, evangelizes on technology, shapes standards, and enables integration across industries. Though it was moving slowly since its foundation, this year (2025) they have regained their original mission at the Data Spaces Symposium.

One of their members, IDSA, during its General Assembly December 2024 (see Figure 12) introduced the IDSA Season 2 to move from the Data Spaces consolidation phase into the Springboard phase with the intention to move from the “Trough of Disillusionment” into the “slope of Enlightenment” by focusing more on market, proving business relevance of Data Spaces.

Fig. 12 Data Spaces become reality-IDSA GA December 2024

This view is also shared by other associations like the Eclipse Foundation though EDWG (Eclipse DataSpace Working Group) where emphasis is placed in “Commercialization” to escape from the “Valley of Death” where they currently are (see Figure 13).

Fig. 13: Data Spaces current status- Eclipse Dataspace

Gaia-X is a common enabler across Cloud-Data-AI European initiatives.

Fig. 14: Gaia-X vision as common enabler

As shown in Figure 14, Gaia-X is a common technical framework that serves to align objectives, technologies, and governance models of various initiatives, under a unifying framework for digital transparency, interoperability, and trust. By acting as a neutral, open, and inclusive enabler, the Gaia-X trust framework ensures that each initiative can both –contribute to- and –benefit from- shared digital infrastructures, reducing fragmentation and maximising impact.

Synergies creation above different initiatives:

- Dynamo Cloud⁷ and Fulcrum⁸ can provide complementary offerings to the European cloud market based on Gaia-X compliance
- Marketplaces like DOME⁹ (Figure 15) and CISPE Cloud¹⁰ can leverage Gaia-’s TCK to ensure its decentralised marketplace harmonised cloud offerings across catalogues.
- Simpl-Open can connect infrastructure offerings listed under DOME following Data Spaces’ requirements for Gaia-X Labels.

Gaia-X is also aligning with other Trust Frameworks like iShare¹¹ to enable compliance with EU regulations (Data Act, CRA, DGA) which are the basis for Data Sovereignty. Cloud-Edge-IoT service offerings can get the complaint level from the Clearing houses and guarantee the fulfilment of the regulation to all participants in the Trust framework enabling the “Data flows with Trust”.

Fig. 15: DOME marketplace

The different associations are working to address the significant challenge that Europe is facing in the digital landscape, with a growing productivity gap between the EU and the US,

⁷ [Dynamo: Unlocking the power of the new European cloud and data ecosystem](#)

⁸ [Computing Exchange Market - Fulcrum](#)

⁹ [DOME Marketplace](#)

¹⁰ [CISPE.cloud](#)

¹¹ [iSHARE](#)

driven primarily by digital technology. According to the Draghi Report, the EU needs to promote cross-industry coordination and data sharing to accelerate the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into European industry. However, Europe is falling behind in breakthrough digital technologies, with 70% of AI foundation models developed in the US since 2017, and

65% of the global and European cloud market is controlled by just three US hyperscalers. This is despite the fact that AI is a key driver of economic growth and innovation¹², and that Europe produces massive amounts of industrial data. Unfortunately, this data remains largely siloed within companies and industries, hindering its potential to fuel competitive AI and drive innovation¹³.

A major step towards digital sovereignty has been taken with the convergence of the work of the various associations to bridge the US-EU divide, and already European cloud customers are considering moving away from US hyperscalers¹⁴.

Increasing access to high-quality data is also a key component of the EU's EdgeCloudIoT strategy. Some proposed actions include:

- **Creating a single market for data:** The data union strategy aims to create a true internal market for data, allowing for the scaling up of AI development across the EU. This will facilitate the creation of large, high-quality datasets that can be shared and used by various stakeholders, including researchers, developers, and industries. By creating a single market for data, the EU can:
 - Foster collaboration and innovation across industries and countries
 - Reduce data fragmentation and siloing
 - Increase the availability of data for AI development and training
- **Data labs within AI factories:** The creation of data labs within AI factories will provide researchers and developers with the tools they need to innovate. These data labs will gather and organize high-quality data from diverse sources, making it easier to develop and train advanced AI models. This will:
 - Improve the quality and diversity of data available for AI development
 - Reduce the barriers to entry for new AI developers and researchers
 - Enable the development of more accurate and effective AI models
- By addressing the need for high-quality data, the EU can:
 - a. **Improve AI development and innovation:** Access to high-quality data is essential for developing and training advanced AI models. By creating a single market for data and providing data labs within AI factories, the EU can foster AI innovation and development across the continent.
 - b. **Enhance competitiveness:** The availability of high-quality data can give European industries a competitive edge in the global market. By creating a single market for data and providing access to high-quality datasets, the EU

¹² European Commission: Directorate-General for Economic and Financial Affairs, Simons, W., Turrini, A., & Vivian, L. (2024). *Artificial intelligence : economic impact, opportunities, challenges, implications for policy*, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2765/48272>

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¹³ [The Draghi report on EU competitiveness](#)

¹⁴ [Europe's cloud customers eyeing exit from US hyperscalers • The Register](#)

can enhance the competitiveness of its industries and support economic growth.

The convergence of various initiatives, including data spaces, is a crucial component in achieving European digital sovereignty and cross-industry coordination. The 6G-IA initiative is a notable example of this effort, demonstrating a strong focus on collaboration and cross-industry coordination over the past year.

Since July 2024, the 6G-IA has been actively involved in several initiatives aimed at strengthening European digital sovereignty and fostering cross-industry coordination. One of the key actions was the signing of a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the European Rail Infrastructure Managers Association (EIM) on December 10, 2024. This MoU aims to enhance digital integration across the rail industry, promoting the adoption of advanced 6G technologies to improve operational efficiency and safety.¹⁵

In addition, the 6G-IA has been advocating for increased investment in European research and innovation through collaborative efforts. On July 4, 2024, the association, along with 110 other European RD&I stakeholders, issued a joint statement urging EU institutions to significantly increase funding for the next European Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (FP10). This initiative underscores the commitment to maintaining Europe's competitive edge in the global digital landscape.¹⁶

NexusForum.EU continues to foster its connection with the 6G-IA initiative through its partnership with OpenNebula. To further strengthen this collaboration, they have, for example, actively participated in various brokerage events, creating opportunities for knowledge sharing, networking, and potential future collaborations between NexusForum.EU and 6G-IA stakeholders.

To effectively engage with the different organizations the following strategies can be proposed, grouped into dimensions of engagement:

1. Strategic Alignment & Policy Advocacy

- o Leverage DSBA's unified front: NexusForum will facilitate structured dialogues between EU institutions and DSBA's member organizations (Gaia-X, BDVA, FIWARE, IDSA) to coordinate joint policy recommendations for digital sovereignty, interoperability, and industrial data sharing.
- o Support Gaia-X as a common enabler: Position NexusForum as a policy bridge between Gaia-X's trust framework and EU legislative bodies (e.g., for the Data Act, DGA, CRA), ensuring feedback from real-world implementation reaches regulators.
- o Amplify IDSA Season 2 objectives: Co-develop policy briefs with IDSA to demonstrate market traction and business relevance of data spaces, assisting their Springboard phase with regulatory clarity and investment incentives.

2. Community Building & Capacity Development

¹⁵https://6g-ia.eu/single_post/?slug=eim-and-6g-ia-sign-a-memorandum-of-understanding

¹⁶https://6g-ia.eu/single_post/?slug=joint-statement-for-an-ambitious-fp10-investing-in-europes-future-competitive-ness-through-collaborative-research-development-and-innovation

- o Facilitate AI-Factory pilots: Through NexusForum, help coordinate cross-sector data lab initiatives, linking BDVA, IDSA, and national AI initiatives to real industrial use cases with EU-level funding.
- o Organize joint events and working groups: Co-host summits or workshops (e.g., during Data Spaces Symposium or European Research & Innovation Days) where NexusForum provides structured formats for aligning EU priorities with community actions.
- o Launch Digital Sovereignty Talent Taskforce: In collaboration with DSBA members, promote workforce development initiatives around data stewardship, AI, and compliance engineering.

3. Monitoring, Evidence & Impact Reporting

- o Policy readiness assessments: Partner with associations to identify bottlenecks in regulatory implementation(e.g., Gaia-X label adoption, data sharing trust barriers) and propose tailored policy solutions.
- o Support EU competitiveness benchmarking: Using data from the Draghi report and market studies, assess Europe's digital productivity gaps, linking them with policy recommendations on AI, cloud, and data infrastructure.

Overall, the proposed actions can help address the EU's requirements for EdgeCloudIoT strategy by providing access to high-quality data, fostering AI innovation and development, and enhancing competitiveness.

5.1.2 From EUCloudEdgeIoT to Open Source AI¹⁷

5.1.2.1 Open Source as a competitive advantage

Open Source software delivers strategic advantages to every organization that is undergoing, driving, or developing digital transformation initiatives - from corporations and governments to research and academic institutions. As imperatives such as citizen privacy, digital competitiveness, and independence from proprietary, locked-in solutions become increasingly important in the European policy discourse, Open Source is considered a key factor toward European digital sovereignty. This can be observed in regulatory and policy instruments such as the Digital Services Act¹⁸, the General Data Protection Regulation¹⁹, the Competitiveness Compass²⁰, as well as other impactful elements in the European landscape.

¹⁷ [*Input from the Eclipse Foundation*](#)

¹⁸ [*The EU's Digital Services Act*](#)

¹⁹ [*Regulation - 2016/679 - EN - gdpr - EUR-Lex*](#)

²⁰ [*Competitiveness compass - European Commission*](#)

5.1.2.2 Maximizing impact with business-friendly, community-driven Open Source

To maximize the long-term impact of research results, Open Source is a powerful vehicle - provided it is done right. Building, strengthening, and growing a successful Open Source ecosystem requires several key elements: the use of proven processes and best practices for vendor-neutral governance, effective intellectual property (IP) management, and licensing code under business-friendly licenses such as EPL-2.0, Apache-2.0, BSD, or MIT. In addition, community building and dissemination activities to boost visibility and adoption of the project.

5.1.2.3 Building on the success of the Open Source EUCloudEdgeloT ecosystem

EUCloudEdgeloT.eu can be considered a starting point for putting stronger emphasis on building Open Source ecosystems with European research projects (manifested in the Task Force “Open Source Engagement” led by Eclipse Foundation). With the MetaOS/Cognitive Cloud and similar project clusters coming to an end we see first results finding their way into the Open Source communities where they will hopefully thrive and become cornerstones of the European EUCloudEdgeloT community and its subsequent initiatives to build the AI continent²¹. As part of our strategy for Open Source AI in the European ecosystem, we foresee to build tighter connections between the research clusters such as EUCloudEdgeloT/NexusForum.EU (and the upcoming AI calls) and the emerging Eclipse Open Source AI communities around projects such as Eclipse Aidge, Eclipse LMOS, Eclipse GRAPHENE or Eclipse Theia AI.

5.1.2.4 The way forward: Eclipse Foundation vision for Open Source AI (OSAI)

The Eclipse Foundation’s vision for Open Source AI aligns with the broader goal of making AI development open and collaborative. Through initiatives like the partnership with the Open Source Initiative (OSI)²², the Foundation is creating an ecosystem for Open Source AI that is not only powerful but also trustworthy and vendor-neutral, enabling communities and organizations - especially in Europe - to build AI solutions that support digital sovereignty. With AI regulation on the horizon in multiple regions, including the EU, the Eclipse Foundation also recognises the need to help policymakers understand the unique challenges and opportunities of Open Source AI technologies. The fast-paced advancement of AI, coupled with emerging, complex regulatory frameworks, requires clear, consistent, and unified guidance based on Open Source principles.

5.1.2.5 Open Specifications for Open Source AI

The Eclipse Specification Process (EFSP) is a governance model by the Eclipse Foundation to develop open, community-driven software specifications. It ensures transparency, vendor neutrality, and compatibility through structured phases, public participation, and the use of Technology Compatibility Kits (TCKs). While not a formal standards body like ISO or W3C, EFSP supports the creation of open standards by promoting implementable and freely accessible specifications, making it a modern alternative to traditional standardization

²¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52025DC0165>

²² <https://newsroom.eclipse.org/news/announcements/OpenSource-initiative-and-eclipse-foundation-collaborate-shaping-Open-Source-ai>

processes. Open specifications are important for Open Source AI ecosystems because they promote collaboration, transparency, interoperability, and accessibility, fostering innovation and adoption.

5.1.2.6 Recommendations for Research programmes

In line with the work conducted in the SWOT analysis for Work Package 3 (see D.3.2. for reference) of the NexusForum.EU, these are the specific recommendations for Research programme:

- Implement Open Source properly in research projects to maximize impact and achieve long term sustainability of research results enabling wide adoption and commercialization.
- Use business-friendly licenses such as EPL-2.0, Apache-2.0, BSD, or MIT.
- Foster cross-collaboration and community building across research projects and existing Open Source communities.
- An Open Source strategy should be a mandatory part of every research project's sustainability roadmap.

5.2 Engagement with relevant EU institutions and agencies

ENISA

ENISA (European Union Agency for Network and Information Security) has a clear position on the future of the Cloud Continuum. In their reports and guidelines, they have highlighted the evolution of cloud computing and its impact on the future of cloud security. This materializes in the creation of the EUCS candidate scheme (European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme) which looks into the cybersecurity of cloud services. The EUCS first draft was published in December 2020 for open consultation and is currently under development in the phase of receiving feedback from the EU Member States. In the context of this consultation phase, some stakeholders created the “EUCS High +”²³ initiative, which claims that EUCS includes High+ criteria, including data residency requirements and requiring at a minimum EU sovereign control of key elements for security and encryption.

Overall, ENISA's position on the Cloud Continuum emphasizes the need for a proactive, risk-based approach to cloud security, leveraging AI and ML, and promoting cross-industry collaboration to ensure a secure and resilient cloud ecosystem.

In the context of European Data Strategy²⁴, the EU and ENISA are also working on the development of the EU Cloud Rulebook, a single, European-wide framework that outlines binding and non-binding rules for cloud service users and providers in Europe. The Rulebook aims to provide clarity, consistency, and coherence in the cloud market, facilitating a more efficient and secure use of cloud services. It contributes to the EU's broader strategy of promoting a secure and sustainable digital landscape. In addition, the Rulebook will consider the growing importance of edge computing, including requirements for secure, sustainable, and interoperable edge computing architectures. It will also provide guidelines for the design, deployment, and operation of cloud infrastructures, ensuring security, sustainability, and interoperability across different cloud services and providers.

²³ <https://eucshighplus.eu/>

²⁴ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cloud-computing>

5.3 Engagement with the non-EU R&D community

Based on the input obtained from the EU-JAPAN Digital Week event held in Tokio 31st march-7th April 2025, the engagement between Europe and Japan focused on cooperation in the areas of AI regulation, innovation, and societal impact.

Cooperation in AI Regulation: Both Japan and Europe can benefit from sharing regulatory approaches and best practices in AI governance. Japan's 3-pillar framework (promotion of AI technologies, sector-specific regulatory approach, and international partnerships) can be explored in more detail, and Europe can share its own experiences in AI regulation. This cooperation can help address the challenge of identifying which AI technologies to use and how to ensure safety and responsibility in AI development.

Addressing the Innovation Crisis: Sebastien Lechevalier's²⁵ observation about the gap between innovation resources and output in terms of wellbeing is relevant to both Japan and Europe. Both regions can explore new models of innovation that prioritize social needs and wellbeing, rather than just competitiveness. This could involve cooperative research efforts, joint policy initiatives, and innovation ecosystem development.

Joint Research and Development: Japan and Europe can collaborate on joint research and development projects in areas such as AI, IoT, and other emerging technologies. This can help address common challenges, such as the aging society and the need for more effective and responsible innovation.

Business Opportunities and Technological Outcomes: As Hiroki Habuka²⁶ mentioned, there are significant business opportunities and technological outcomes to be expected from Japan-EU cooperation. Both regions can explore joint ventures, partnerships, and other forms of collaboration to drive innovation and economic growth.

Direction in Technological Progress: Sebastien Lechevalier emphasized the need for a certain direction in technological progress, one that prioritizes social needs and wellbeing. Japan and Europe can work together to establish a shared vision for responsible innovation and technological development, one that addresses common challenges and promotes mutual benefits.

Possible Areas of Cooperation:

- AI governance and regulation
- Joint research and development in emerging technologies
- Innovation ecosystem development and policy initiatives
- Cooperation in standardization and certification
- Joint business ventures and partnerships

Benefits of Cooperation:

- Improved regulatory frameworks for AI and emerging technologies
- Enhanced innovation ecosystem and research cooperation
- Increased business opportunities and economic growth
- Shared knowledge and best practices in responsible innovation
- Stronger partnerships and cooperation in addressing common challenges

²⁵ Visiting researcher, German institute for Japanese Studies

²⁶ Research professor, Graduate school of law, Kyoto University; CEO, Smart Governance

6 Conclusions

This deliverable reports on the progress made in stakeholder engagement and community-building activities since the previous Report (M6) up until the current reporting month (June 2025). Through a range of targeted efforts, the project has successfully established itself as a strategic coordination and engagement hub at the intersection of EU research, industry, and policy around the emerging Cognitive Computing Continuum. These engagement efforts were closely aligned with the IPCEI-CIS and the Cloud-Edge Working Group of the European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud, ensuring maximum policy relevance and impact.

The key conclusions from engagement activities to date (M18) include:

- The establishment of thematic and geographic Working Groups (WGs). This has proven to be a cornerstone of NexusForum.EU's engagement strategy. Each WG is co-led by a research institution and an EU-based industry stakeholder, ensuring balanced and expert input. The WGs serve not only as knowledge exchange platforms but also as operational mechanisms to contribute directly to the Research & Innovation Roadmap. The alignment of WGs with the IPCEI-CIS Workstreams and the Cloud-Edge WG Task Forces of the Alliance ensures that the community building effort directly supports Europe's strategic industrial priorities.
- The alignment of stakeholder consensus on the need for defining "European Open Source". The engagement has shown a growing demand for a shared definition of European Open Source that balances global openness with European control and sovereignty objectives. This reflects input from academic institutions and industry partners alike, and forms the basis for future roadmap updates and EC policy recommendations.
- The definition of cross-border cooperation as a key driver. Indeed, international engagement, - particularly through the EU-Japan WG and upcoming EU-South Korea WG, has opened new pathways for collaboration in areas such as cloud security, AI governance, and joint R&I projects. The workshop held in Tokyo during EU-Japan Digital Week and participation from entities like KOIIA, JBCE, and the EU-Japan Centre for Industrial Cooperation are practical examples of this strategic outreach.
- The concrete alignment with the broader EU digital policy landscape. This is the result of NexusForum.EU acting as a focal point for integrating a wide range of initiatives, from Gaia-X and IDSA to 6G-IA and BDVA. This alignment has enabled the project to channel feedback into policy processes and to contribute to the ongoing convergence efforts across Europe's digital ecosystem.

A final version of this report, to be produced in M30 (June 2026) will offer an update on those activities.

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Appendix A - SovereignEdge.eu Blog Posts

As part of its commitment to actively engage with the European market, and by leveraging the resources of SovereignEdge.EU—a community initiative coordinated by OpenNebula Systems and focused on bringing together the main EU industrial and research organisations collaborating in the sustainable development of European Open Source cloud/edge technologies—the NexusForum.EU Project has launched a series of public interviews with EU industry leaders and technology experts. These interviews offer valuable information for understanding to what extent the Roadmaps produced by the CSA are aligned with the main technological and digital policy priorities of the EU industry.

For a critical digital infrastructure in our own hands – An exclusive interview with Octavia de Weerd (NBIP)

An exclusive interview with Octavia de Weerd, General Director of NBIP

Link: [For a critical digital infrastructure in our own hands – An exclusive interview with Octavia de Weerd \(NBIP\) | SovereignEdge.EU](#)

Octavia de Weerd is General Director of NBIP. She has extensive experience in IT, internet technology, cyber security and organizational governance, having fulfilled various leadership roles during her 30-year career. At NBIP, she is currently at the helm of various European funded projects the non-for-profit participates in, including the IPCEI-CIS. She is a European at heart and strongly believes in the strength of collaborative action.

What is NBIP and how have you been contributing so far to the IPCEI-CIS?

NBIP is a Dutch foundation that provides professional cyber security services to providers and organisations in the digital infrastructure sector, based on the idea that an open and resilient Internet is a shared responsibility. We therefore operate on a non-for-profit basis to achieve this goal.

NBIP operates and develops facilities from a shared service center concept. This enables providers and organisations using the internet, to comply with legal and availability requirements. These facilities are costly to acquire, operate and maintain as a single party. Therefore, it makes sense to jointly operate such services. An example of such a facility is our not-for-profit DDoS scrubbing center NaWas, which currently services some 200 organisations in 10 European countries.

Our role in the IPCEI-CIS lies primarily in developing a secure by design open security platform that will be integrated in the stack of a new modular data center design for a distributed European cloud infrastructure. One of the avenues we are currently exploring in this regard is a distributed edge DDoS mitigation platform. We also have a very active role in the cross-cutting security workstream which involves many IPCEI-CIS projects.

How important is it to foster a model of joint technological innovation for strengthening the global competitiveness of the EU cloud industry?

I think it would be, at this moment in time, hard to overstate the significance of cooperation for technological innovation in the EU, especially in the digital domain. We are now rapidly becoming more aware of what risks are associated with outsourcing much of our needs for digital technology and services to non-EU corporations. I believe the EU has taken and is taking important steps to reduce these risks, for example by investing in programs to realize its own cloud infrastructure. But this will take time, perseverance, and a shift in mentality. What I mean by that is that I think it should be self-evident to everyone that Europe will only be able to prosper if we cooperate more and more often and put our collective interests as Europeans above other concerns.

How do you understand the concept of “European digital sovereignty”, and what role should cybersecurity play in that?

In the past decades we have created dependencies on foreign technology and services that in hindsight seem undesirable. There are many circumstances that have led to these dependencies, and I don't think it is useful to dwell too much on the past. We do need to carefully consider now, nevertheless, how we are going to disentangle ourselves from non-EU tech. When we talk about digital sovereignty, we should understand it as a certain level of control over the digital technology we use, whether it's hardware, software, or the infrastructure we use to deliver digital services. Open Source solutions are an important way to achieve this.

This is also true for cybersecurity. Many cybersecurity services and applications that are used across Europe have not been developed within the EU. Given the current geopolitical context, we cannot rule out that this will one day be turned against us. Does that mean we need to become a digital autarky? Of course not. This would harm us more than it would do good. But we do need to think carefully about what it means to be digitally sovereign in a world that is thoroughly digitally interconnected.

I think a sensible first step would be to ensure that critical digital infrastructure is firmly in our own hands. In addition, we need to move away from using non-EU cloud services for anything and everything, without much regard for the (national) security risks associated with it. When it comes to cybersecurity, we need to be able to develop and provide core services ourselves, whether it is DDoS-mitigation, AV-software, or firewalls.

How do you perceive recent EU regulatory initiatives such as the Cyber Resilience Act?

I think that, as Europeans, we should be proud that the EU is taking the lead and setting an example when it comes to regulating the digital domain, including cyber resilience. In my view, many issues around cybersecurity are the result of two things: non-intentional incompetence and a classic collective action problem. What I mean is that many organizations that need to be more cyber resilient, fail to achieve this because they do not know they are falling short in this respect.

Secondly, issues such as the abuse of security vulnerabilities are enabled by the fact that it's not always in the interest of organizations to commit resources to solving these types of problems, even though if everyone would take it seriously, the problem would be less persistent and less costly. So it helps to have clear rules about what is expected from

manufacturers and developers in this respect, which will hopefully ultimately result in less abuse.

Technological challenges aside, what do you think is the main digital policy aspect that the EU should address in the short-mid term?

I think we are on the right track, but I think the EU should be wary of over-regulating the digital sector. It is difficult for many SMEs to keep up with the regulations that have been enacted in the past years. These regulations are necessary, there is no doubt about that. But we also run the risk that SMEs, who play an important role in ensuring Europe's digital sovereignty by participating in European funded projects, will refrain from participating and boosting innovation. For them, a steep regulatory burden is stifling their capacity for innovation. I would therefore say the EU should be mindful of this if it wants its ambitious projects to come to fruition sooner rather than later.

Building Europe's Computing Continuum based on interoperability – An exclusive interview with Björn Håkansson (TNO)

An exclusive interview with Björn Håkansson, Senior Business Development Manager at TNO.

Link: [Building Europe's Computing Continuum based on interoperability – An exclusive interview with Björn Håkansson \(TNO\) | SovereignEdge.EU](#)

You were recently elected as Co-Chair of the Cloud-Edge Working Group of the European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud. In which way is this initiative crucial in the current technological and geopolitical context?

I think the *European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud* plays a crucial role in creating a stable meeting point for the industry and the European Commission, where we can share our views on the developing technologies and developing markets around Cloud-Edge in Europe. As industry partners in the Alliance we have the opportunity to advise the European Commission on both the larger picture as well as on details that may be important to all of us. There is a lot going on both in the technological domain as well as in the geopolitical arena so this is an important moment for Europe, especially in the digital field of Cloud and Edge.

How do you understand the concept of “European digital sovereignty” and how does it inspire the activities that the Cloud-Edge WG undertakes?

European digital sovereignty is one of the triggers on many interesting discussions in the market. Basically it means that users in Europe want to have better control over their digital environments. This can however be achieved in multiple ways; more transparency is a key instrument in this, more choice of providers and avoiding lock-in effects are other ways. Also non-EU providers are taking steps to offer more digital sovereignty in their services, and then it often comes down to taking a risk-based approach. Are the potential risks around digital sovereignty manageable in relation to the benefits of opting for a very capable non-European provider? The Cloud-Edge WG can undertake activities to promote more transparency, more interoperability and more awareness around the factors that are important for European digital sovereignty. For individual companies there will also be other considerations than for EU Member States and the European Union as a whole, where for the latter digital autonomy, fair markets, technological competitiveness and longer-term dependencies will be key factors. This complex landscape inspires us to guide our stakeholders towards the different enablers needed so that European players can compete and become capable providers in a thriving European digital landscape otherwise dominated by the larger non-European players.

How important is it to foster a model of joint technological innovation for strengthening the global competitiveness of the EU industry?

I think there is no other way than joint technological innovation. In certain domains, like cloud services or AI, the European developments are lagging behind the larger non-EU developments and this can partly be blamed on the fragmented European market and some other deficiencies that were highlighted well in the recent Draghi Report. To stay competitive in the EU we need to target the obstacles that are holding us back, one of which is interoperability on a European scale. Interoperability is nothing you can develop without joint technological innovation. The development of a common reference architecture, of common open standards, and of the technological solutions often based on Open Source software are all made possible only through joint technological innovation. How to achieve that? That often requires strong incentives, like facilitated collaboration and access to shared funding for research and innovation. In the Netherlands, for example, TNO operates a government-funded Centre of Excellence for Data Sharing and Cloud that provides a whole range of activities aimed at fostering collaboration.

How do you expect the new European highly-distributed, multi-provider cloud infrastructure that projects like the IPCEI-CIS are building will speed up the consolidation of the Edge Computing paradigm?

I think the IPCEI-CIS is a very good example of how much the EU can facilitate collaboration and provide access to shared funding. The Edge Computing paradigm will also be an integral part of the next generation of cloud infrastructure and services where a multi-provider based computing continuum will be working seamlessly across Europe. There is still however the need to do more in order to speed up and consolidate this tendency further; the IPCEI-CIS will contribute of course, but maybe additional IPCEIs might be needed to target areas not covered in the IPCEI-CIS. An important part to discover is also how European telcos can play a role in the digital Edge Computing landscape, and how this role integrates with—and complements—the overarching multi-provider cloud-edge continuum.

Technological challenges aside, what do you think is the main digital policy aspect related to cloud/edge computing that the EU should address in the short-mid term?

We have seen that legislation can be important too; the Data Act serves as a good example where digital policy can contribute to developments in the short/mid-term. However, we also notice that many users and many providers are frustrated and struggling to understand what is going on and what to expect, and when things are happening. They often hear about European projects like IPCEI-CIS, initiatives like Gaia-X, enablers like SIMPL and DOME, and compliance requirements such as EUCS and NIS2. However, they don't always see the forest through the trees. For those working on digital policies I think a short-term aspect would be to increase awareness of all that is happening and what users and providers can expect. The different roadmaps from our WG could play a role here. A mid-term aspect that might also help is to enable some leading examples, e.g. by having the EU co-funding a pilot project to showcase and demonstrate some of the new developments. There are already a lot of interesting things happening, but we need to make sure that companies in Europe (including SMEs) know about them too.

Appendix B - NexusForum.EU's Smart Computing and Connectivity Workshop

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 Which specific areas of the roadmap do you believe should receive more focus to better align with Japan's national priorities? (Choose top 3 priorities)

Multiple Choice Poll 17 participants

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 Which aspects of AI developments does Japan prioritize the most? (choose 1)

Multiple Choice Poll 17 participants

slido

 To those of you who have answered “Deploying and using AI in industry applications”, which specific applications do you foresee being more impactful in Japan?

Open text poll 5 participants

- Anonymous
Contents generation for various applications.
- Anonymous
Mobility
- Anonymous
AI for Health Data Sharing
- Anonymous
health and social care for robotics
- Anonymous
manufacturing

slido

 The energy use of data centres is growing rapidly, especially with the development and deployment of AI technologies. How do you expect Japan to counter the energy and sustainability costs of this growth?

Multiple Choice Poll 13 participants

Energy-efficient data centre operations - 3 votes

Carbon-emissions-aware computing - 2 votes

New software development and software engineering practices - 2 votes

New energy-efficient AI model architectures - 2 votes

Alternative semiconductor and processing technologies - 4 votes

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 As explained earlier, Horizon Europe the largest funding programme for research and innovation in Europe. EU and Japan have recently launched formal discussions on the association of Japan to Horizon Europe. How much do you know about Horizon Europe?

Multiple Choice Poll 15 participants

A lot - 3 votes

A moderate amount - 5 votes

Not much - 4 votes

Nothing - 3 votes

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🗳️ If Japan becomes an associated country to the funding programme Horizon Europe, do you see your organisation apply for collaborative research projects? (choose 1)

Multiple Choice Poll 13 votes 13 participants

Yes - 12 votes

No - 1 vote

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🗳️ From your perspective, which are the main benefits of enabling cross-border data flows between Japan and EU?

Multiple Choice Poll 12 votes 12 participants

Less regulatory burden, as your company only needs to follow the legislation of your own region, regardless of the data's origin. - 2 votes

Widen the market opportunities for your services. - 2 votes

More and diverse data available to train AI systems, reducing regional biases. - 5 votes

Build collaborative DataSpaces with participants from both regions. - 3 votes

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 How important is Technological Sovereignty perceived in Japan’s smart connectivity and computing ecosystem?

Multiple Choice Poll 11 participants

Very important - 6 votes

Important - 3 votes

Not important - 2 votes

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 How important is Technological Sovereignty perceived in Japan’s smart connectivity and computing ecosystem?

Multiple Choice Poll 11 participants

Very important - 6 votes

Important - 3 votes

Not important - 2 votes

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 What do you think is the best strategy to close the gap with vendor lock-in solutions provided by hyperscalers (Google, Microsoft, AWS, Alibaba, Tencent ..) in the market?

Multiple Choice Poll 13 participants

Continue relying on hyperscalers: Keep the current market situation and allow hyperscalers to provide vendor-lock in solutions while they comply with EU/Japan regulations. - 0 votes

Collaborate with hyperscalers: EU/Japan cloud service providers (CSPs) partnering with hyperscalers, provided they comply with EU and Japan regulations. - 4 votes

Develop Japanese and/or EU hyperscalers that are subject to EU and Japan regulations. - 0 votes

Develop an alternative model that relies on an open ecosystem to federate and combine resources from many smaller providers, that is subject to EU and Japan regulations. - 9 votes

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Appendix C – Working Group Co-Leaders table

Name	Affiliation	Working Group	Reason for election as Working Group Co-Leader
David Artuñedo	Telefónica	Telco Cloud-Edge	David has a background in computer science engineering and is currently working as the CEO of OnLife Networks, an internal Telefonica start-up. He is leading a team of 15 people with the aim of defining a new Architecture for Central Offices based in OCP Hardware and Open Source NFV and SDN Software. As a Telco Cloud-Edge WG Co-Leader, he brings 20 years of experience in the telco and innovation domains.
Anders Lindgren	RISE	Telco Cloud-Edge	Anders is a senior researcher with extensive experience. He received his Ph.D. from Luleå University of Technology in 2006 and worked at University College London and the University of Cawas. He has migrated much of his DTN research experience into his ICN research and is currently investigating the use of ICN technology for IoT applications. His work also covers areas such as 5G, Computing Continuum and neuromorphic AI.
Antonio Álvarez	OpenNebula Systems	AI for Cloud-Edge	Antonio is the PO Manager for EU funded projects at OpenNebula Systems. As the AI for Cloud-Edge Working Group Co-Leader he brings extensive experience in EU funded projects, and a solid technical background. He holds a Master of Engineering in Automation, Robotics and Computer Networks and throughout his career he has worked on projects involving mobile networks, programming and automation. He is involved in other EU CSAs, as well as in the IPCEI-CIS.
Ian Marsh	RISE	AI for Cloud-Edge	Ian is a senior researcher at RISE, who brings more than 30 years of experience to his AI for Cloud-Edge Working Group co-leading role. His

			latest works focused on Big data/Machine learning projects for the European automotive sectors; fundamentals for big data processing, machine learning and platforms needed to process large amounts of data; ML algorithms, sensor, log and maintenance data; and latency reduction cases. He has worked for numerous engineering projects involving European industries.
Antal Kuthy	E-Group	Cloud-Edge for AI	Antal is the CEO and founder of E-Group ICT Software & Innovation Group. He has a diverse educational background, ranging from software and electrical engineering to telecommunication, finance, cryptography, information theory and natural language processing.
Björn Forsberg	RISE	Cloud-Edge for AI	Björn is a senior researcher at RISE. He holds a PhD in Timing Predictable Execution for Heterogeneous Embedded Systems from ETH Zürich and a MSc in Information Technology Engineering from Uppsala Universitet. As Co-Leader of the Cloud-Edge for AI Working Group, he brings a multitude of interests: new and enabling technologies at the hardware/software boundary, and its impact on system programmability, real-time properties, and performance. His interests also include computer architecture with a focus towards memory systems and real-time scheduling for energy-efficiency, and compilers.
Giovanni Frattini	Engineering	Cloud-Edge Use Cases	Giovanni has a background in physics and cybernetics and is currently working as Head of Research and Innovation at Engineering. He is also a member of the 8RA Facilitation Group. In this role, he supports a large group of companies working on applications exploiting the benefits of the multi-provider cloud continuum. In previous roles he has gained valuable experience in European Research and Innovation initiatives.
Dimosthenis Kyriazis	Univ. of Piraeus	Cloud-Edge Use	Dimosthenis is a professor and vice-rector at the University of Piraeus. He holds a PhD in the area

		Cases	of Service Oriented Architectures with a focus on quality aspects and workflow management. His expertise lies in service-based, distributed, and heterogeneous systems, software engineering, and data management. He has participated in several EU and National funded projects, and he is currently focusing on data management, virtualization technologies for high-availability in cloud and edge environments, as well as socially-enhanced techniques for IoT management – coordinating EU funded projects that target these areas, while also analyzing topics related to big data management and content syndication.
Arthur van der Wees	Arthur's Legal	Cybersecurity	Arthur is the founder of Arthur’s Legal and his legal experience covers a wide range of technological topics, among which is cybersecurity. He has also held the position of expert at the European Commission, in the Expert Group B2B Data Sharing and Cloud Computing Contracts, helping to shape the outcome of the Data Act. As a cybersecurity working group Co-Leader, he brings the necessary expertise needed to understand cybersecurity issues from the industrial point of view, having worked on a number of cases on this and related issues.
Iraklis Symeonidis	RISE	Cybersecurity	Iraklis Symeonidis is a Senior Research Scientist at RISE, specializing in cybersecurity and privacy. He focuses on information security governance, secure architectures, compliance frameworks, and risk mitigation strategies. With expertise in threat analysis and the design of cyber-resilient and privacy-preserving systems for real-world applications, Iraklis contributes to Sweden’s research and innovation efforts, particularly in advancing the digitalization of industrial systems. He works to protect digital ecosystems supporting critical and connected infrastructure. As a cybersecurity working group Co-Leader, he brings the necessary expertise needed to understand and address complex cybersecurity challenges, bridging research with practical applications and effectively engaging

			stakeholders at both technical and management levels.
Antje Raetzer Scheibe	T-Systems (Deutsche Telekom)	Sustainability	Antje currently works as a sustainability expert at T-Systems. She has been sharing her expertise in the field for the past 20 years.
Jon Summers	RISE	Sustainability	Jon is the scientific leader in Data Centers at RISE and he also holds other academic positions in highly ranked academic institutions. As a Sustainability Working Group Co-Leader, he brings During the last 25 years of experience during which he has worked on a number of government and industry funded projects requiring the use of computation. His latest research has focused on a range of thermal management and energy flow projects within the Data Centre, Heating Ventilation, Air Conditioning, industrial sectors and thermal and energy management of microelectronic systems.
Lukas Rybok	IONOS	Interoperability	Lukas is the Technical Research and Development Leader at IONOS, where he drives innovation across a range of advanced technologies including AI, IoT, and cloud computing. With over 15 years of experience in both academic and industrial research, he specialises in Machine Learning, robotics, computer vision and digital sovereignty. He holds a doctorate in computer science, focusing on applied machine learning and computer vision. At IONOS, Lukas leads cutting-edge R&D projects aimed at transforming innovative ideas into commercially viable products. His work is central to shaping the future of technology through strategic research and development initiatives.
Gorka Benguria	Tecnalía	Interoperability	Gorka is a senior researcher at Tecnalía, where his work extensively focuses on interoperability. He is specialised in high performance analytics within the ICT division. His expertise encompasses cloud computing, system

			architecture, computer networking and virtualisation. Gorka has contributed to over 25 peer-reviewed publications, focusing on areas such as Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC) deployment optimization and multi-objective analysis. He has also explored the integration of rule-based and deep learning approaches for runtime security monitoring in cloud environments. His work supports the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly in fostering innovation and building resilient infrastructure.
Alberto P. Martí	OpenNebula Systems	Sovereignty & Open Source	Alberto is the VP of Open Source Innovation at OpenNebula Systems, where he has been involved in establishing strategic collaborations with public cloud and edge providers, numerous European Open Source initiatives, and development teams from relevant vendors and manufacturers. He is the Chair of the Industry Facilitation Group of the IPCEI-CIS. He is also the Project Coordinator of the Horizon Europe action SovereignEdge.COGNIT, and he is also actively involved in the NexusForum.EU CSA.
Sachiko Muto	RISE	Sovereignty & Open Source	Sachiko is a senior researcher at RISE and the chairman of the OpenFoundation Europe. She has a background in European politics and policy and has devoted most of her career to Open Source advocacy. As a sovereignty and Open Source working group Co-Leader, she brings expert public policy and policy analysis skills, and a vision that entails enabling a value-creating, secure and sustainable consumption, development, and collaboration on Open Source for society at large.
Kazuyuki Shimizu	Meiji University	EU-Japan Cooperation	Kazuyuki is an academic at Meiji University with expertise in cloud computing, edge computing, IoT and industry 4.0. He holds a strong background in computer science and engineering, focusing on the integration and optimization of emerging technologies. His research includes AI applications in cloud and edge systems, enhancing cybersecurity, and solving interoperability challenges in IoT

			environments, with a focus on the automotive industry. His knowledge of both European and Japanese technological landscapes positions him well to co-lead this working group, fostering cross-border collaboration in advances technologies.
Wiktorja Bochenska	Fujitsu	EU-Japan Cooperation	Wiktorja is the EU public affairs manager at Fujitsu, where she focuses on business support and digital policy initiatives. In her role, she works closely with government stakeholders to align Fujitsu’s objectives with evolving regulations, ensuring that the company evolves in synchrony with the global digital transformation. As Vice Chair of the Multilateral Relations Working Group at Digital Europe, she contributes to initiatives that promote global digital innovation. She is also involved with the Japanese Business Council and the European Internet Forum, with a strong interest in the AI Act, the Data Act and the Cyber Resilience Act among other European legislative instruments. With an LLM and an LLB(Hons), along with other prestigious certifications, she combines expertise in international trade, investment and digital policy.